

Table A11 The primary data of this study

NO.	Sex	Age (year)	Subgroup	Date of UBT	DOB (%)	Date of HpSA	HpSA result	Diseases	Medicine
1	male	89	pre-treatment	2007/7/24	32.2	2007/7/19	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
2	male	83	pre-treatment	2007/7/27	54.7	2007/7/24	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Dementia; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
3	male	87	post-treatment	2007/8/21	51.8	2007/8/21	positive	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Coronary heart disease; COPD	
4	male	78	pre-treatment	2007/9/26	9.0	2007/9/28	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
5	male	74	post-treatment	2008/1/8	0.3	2008/1/4	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Opioid analgesics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
6	male	73	pre-treatment	2008/1/22	19.1	2008/1/17	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
7	male	73	pre-treatment	2008/1/22	19.1	2008/1/17	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
8	male	83	pre-treatment	2008/1/23	0.4	2008/1/20	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
9	male	74	post-treatment	2008/2/1	0.9	2008/1/28	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
10	male	81	post-treatment	2008/2/20	0.2	2008/2/18	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
11	male	83	post-treatment	2008/2/21	0.8	2008/2/21	positive	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
12	male	76	pre-treatment	2008/2/22	10.5	2008/2/15	negative	Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
13	male	68	post-treatment	2008/3/5	15.8	2008/3/4	positive	Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
14	male	68	post-treatment	2008/3/31	0.3	2008/3/28	negative		
15	male	79	post-treatment	2008/4/22	0.4	2008/4/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; COPD	
16	male	83	pre-treatment	2008/7/16	12.2	2008/7/16	positive	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
17	male	83	pre-treatment	2008/7/23	13.5	2008/7/16	positive	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
18	male	82	pre-treatment	2008/8/1	0.3	2008/8/1	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
19	male	92	pre-treatment	2008/8/14	1.1	2008/8/15	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
20	male	85	pre-treatment	2008/11/6	7.9	2008/11/7	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents
21	male	75	post-treatment	2008/12/16	0.7	2008/12/12	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
22	male	84	post-treatment	2008/12/18	43.3	2008/12/19	positive	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
23	male	83	pre-treatment	2009/1/6	0.4	2009/1/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Dementia	Antihypertensive agents
24	male	74	pre-treatment	2009/2/18	2.2	2009/2/20	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
25	male	88	post-treatment	2009/2/18	0.4	2009/2/20	negative	GERD; Coronary heart disease; COPD	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents
26	male	75	post-treatment	2009/3/13	0.10	2009/3/10	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps	
27	male	77	pre-treatment	2009/3/23	0.3	2009/3/20	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; COPD; Dementia; Post-cerebral infarction	
28	male	94	post-treatment	2009/4/3	0.1	2009/4/9	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
29	male	80	post-treatment	2009/4/13	0.1	2009/4/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
30	male	65	pre-treatment	2009/4/16	0.2	2009/4/21	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
31	male	68	pre-treatment	2009/4/16	0.1	2009/4/17	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
32	male	78	post-treatment	2009/5/5	18.8	2009/5/8	positive	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
33	male	85	post-treatment	2009/5/5	0.8	2009/4/28	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
34	male	73	pre-treatment	2009/5/7	9.6	2009/5/8	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
35	male	66	pre-treatment	2009/5/12	13.5	2009/5/13	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
36	male	78	post-treatment	2009/5/12	0.1	2009/5/12	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
37	male	77	post-treatment	2009/5/18	0.3	2009/5/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
38	male	78	post-treatment	2009/5/21	0.1	2009/5/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis; COPD	
39	male	69	post-treatment	2009/5/21	0.5	2009/5/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis	

40	male	78	pre-treatment	2009/5/22	0.4	2009/5/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease	
41	male	66	pre-treatment	2009/6/3	14.1	2009/6/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia	Opioid analgesics; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
42	male	72	pre-treatment	2009/6/3	0.5	2009/6/2	negative	Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease	
43	male	88	post-treatment	2009/6/4	1.0	2009/6/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
44	male	66	pre-treatment	2009/6/8	0.6	2009/6/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia	Opioid analgesics; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
45	male	85	pre-treatment	2009/6/25	0.6	2009/6/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Hypertension	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
46	male	86	pre-treatment	2009/6/26	0.5	2009/6/23	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; COPD; Dementia; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents
47	male	89	pre-treatment	2009/7/3	0.7	2009/7/7	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; COPD	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
48	male	71	pre-treatment	2009/7/9	27.7	2009/7/10	positive	GERD; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
49	male	69	post-treatment	2009/7/31	41.8	2009/8/4	negative	Constipation; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
50	male	75	pre-treatment	2009/8/5	14.1	2009/8/7	positive	Constipation; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
51	male	69	post-treatment	2009/8/11	7.4	2009/8/4	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
52	male	68	pre-treatment	2009/8/13	0.6	2009/8/14	negative	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
53	male	91	post-treatment	2009/8/14	0.1	2009/8/14	negative	GERD; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
54	male	84	post-treatment	2009/8/19	1.7	2009/8/14	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; COPD	
55	male	66	pre-treatment	2009/8/25	9.2	2009/8/21	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
56	male	80	pre-treatment	2009/9/23	1.3	2009/9/23	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Post-cerebral infarction	
57	male	81	pre-treatment	2009/9/27	19.8	2009/9/29	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
58	male	74	pre-treatment	2009/10/15	18.60	2009/10/16	intermediate	Colorectal polyps	
59	male	82	post-treatment	2009/10/21	0.4	2009/10/20	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
60	male	65	pre-treatment	2009/10/23	24.0	2009/10/23	negative	Hyperlipidemia	Lipid-lowering agents
61	male	84	post-treatment	2009/10/23	0.6	2009/10/23	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
62	male	77	pre-treatment	2009/10/29	0.9	2009/10/27	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents
63	male	69	post-treatment	2009/11/16	0.1	2009/11/17	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics
64	male	68	pre-treatment	2009/12/2	6.2	2009/12/1	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
65	male	77	post-treatment	2009/12/25	0.7	2009/12/29	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
66	male	69	pre-treatment	2010/1/15	19.5	2010/1/15	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics
67	male	95	pre-treatment	2010/1/21	0.3	2010/1/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
68	male	86	post-treatment	2010/1/21	0.3	2010/1/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
69	male	70	pre-treatment	2010/3/3	0.1	2010/3/2	negative	GERD; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Post-cerebral infarction	
70	male	78	pre-treatment	2010/3/12	0.4	2010/3/12	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; COPD; Dementia; Post-cerebral infarction	
71	male	79	post-treatment	2010/3/15	0.7	2010/3/16	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
72	male	65	post-treatment	2010/3/17	0.6	2010/3/23	negative	Colorectal polyps; Dementia	Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
73	male	72	pre-treatment	2010/3/19	0.5	2010/3/23	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hyperlipidemia	
74	male	79	post-treatment	2010/3/19	0.2	2010/3/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
75	male	68	pre-treatment	2010/3/26	1.0	2010/3/26	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
76	male	77	post-treatment	2010/3/30	0.6	2010/3/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
77	male	65	pre-treatment	2010/3/31	0.7	2010/4/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
78	male	70	post-treatment	2010/4/23	0.40	2010/4/20	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps	
79	male	83	pre-treatment	2010/4/26	29.2	2010/4/27	positive	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Prokinetic agents; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
80	male	86	post-treatment	2010/5/11	6.4	2010/5/18	positive	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents

81	male	79	pre-treatment	2010/5/11	0.2	2010/5/7	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease	
82	male	68	pre-treatment	2010/5/18	0.6	2010/5/18	negative	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
83	male	89	pre-treatment	2010/5/28	3.3	2010/5/28	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
84	male	69	post-treatment	2010/6/11	0.4	2010/6/8	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
85	male	70	post-treatment	2010/6/24	2.0	2010/6/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
86	male	66	pre-treatment	2010/7/13	26.8	2010/7/13	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
87	male	80	pre-treatment	2010/7/15	0.3	2010/7/13	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; History of intestinal surgery; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
88	male	79	pre-treatment	2010/7/27	0.4	2010/7/27	negative	GERD; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
89	male	80	post-treatment	2010/8/6	0.3	2010/8/13	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
90	male	65	post-treatment	2010/9/21	0.4	2010/9/21	negative	Constipation; Hyperlipidemia; Post-cerebral infarction	
91	male	77	post-treatment	2010/9/28	21.6	2010/9/21	positive	Colon diverticulum; Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
92	male	90	post-treatment	2010/10/27	1.3	2010/10/26	negative	GERD; Coronary heart disease; COPD	Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Lipid-lowering agents
93	male	81	pre-treatment	2010/11/18	0.3	2010/11/16	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colon diverticulum; Diabetes mellitus	
94	male	90	pre-treatment	2010/11/29	0.1	2010/11/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
95	male	69	pre-treatment	2010/12/1	0.4	2010/11/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
96	male	73	pre-treatment	2010/12/17	0.3	2010/12/21	negative		
97	male	77	pre-treatment	2010/12/31	0.2	2010/12/31	negative	GERD; Colon diverticulum; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease	Lipid-lowering agents
98	male	70	pre-treatment	2011/3/16	0.1	2011/3/15	negative	Colorectal polyps	Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Lipid-lowering agents
99	male	75	pre-treatment	2011/3/16	0.20	2011/3/15	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
100	male	69	pre-treatment	2011/3/17	0.9	2011/3/22	negative	GERD; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
101	male	87	post-treatment	2011/3/29	0.1	2011/3/29	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
102	male	86	post-treatment	2011/4/8	0.1	2011/4/8	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
103	male	80	post-treatment	2011/4/19	0.4	2011/4/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
104	male	68	pre-treatment	2011/4/29	7.1	2011/5/6	negative	Constipation	
105	male	69	pre-treatment	2011/5/4	27.4	2011/5/6	positive	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; COPD	Opioid analgesics; Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
106	male	87	pre-treatment	2011/5/31	2.9	2011/5/31	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
107	male	66	pre-treatment	2011/6/21	0.2	2011/6/17	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
108	male	66	pre-treatment	2011/6/22	0.6	2011/6/21	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps	Prokinetic agents; Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
109	male	72	post-treatment	2011/6/22	0.3	2011/6/21	negative	Colorectal polyps; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
110	male	86	pre-treatment	2011/6/30	12.0	2011/7/1	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Dementia	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
111	male	79	pre-treatment	2011/6/30	0.8	2011/6/24	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme
112	male	66	post-treatment	2011/7/15	17.70	2011/7/12	intermediate	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Lipid-lowering agents
113	male	88	pre-treatment	2011/7/21	17.5	2011/7/22	positive	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Constipation; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme
114	male	66	post-treatment	2011/8/1	0.2	2011/7/29	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Dementia	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
115	male	78	post-treatment	2011/8/11	1.0	2011/8/12	negative	Colon diverticulum; Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
116	male	80	pre-treatment	2011/8/24	0.7	2011/8/26	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
117	male	79	pre-treatment	2011/9/2	2.6	2011/9/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colon diverticulum; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease	
118	male	74	pre-treatment	2011/9/15	1.5	2011/9/13	negative	GERD; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	
119	male	81	post-treatment	2011/9/16	27.8	2011/9/13	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
120	male	87	post-treatment	2011/9/20	0.1	2011/9/16	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
121	male	78	pre-treatment	2011/10/9	0.4	2011/10/8	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents

122	male	81	pre-treatment	2011/10/11	14.80	2011/10/11	intermediate		Antiplatelet agents
123	male	71	pre-treatment	2011/10/18	0.1	2011/10/14	negative	Gastric polyps; COPD	Digestive enzyme
124	male	84	pre-treatment	2011/11/8	0.7	2011/11/4	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
125	male	71	post-treatment	2011/11/10	0.1	2011/11/4	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
126	male	70	post-treatment	2011/12/1	1.9	2011/11/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease	Opioid analgesics; Digestive enzyme
127	male	82	post-treatment	2011/12/6	35.4	2011/12/2	negative		
128	male	83	pre-treatment	2011/12/23	0.60	2011/12/16	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
129	male	78	pre-treatment	2011/12/27	2.1	2011/12/27	negative	GERD; Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease	Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
130	male	82	pre-treatment	2012/1/17	0.5	2012/1/13	negative	Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
131	male	87	post-treatment	2012/2/3	0.1	2012/2/3	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents
132	male	85	pre-treatment	2012/2/24	0.80	2012/2/21	intermediate	GERD; Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents
133	male	68	pre-treatment	2012/2/28	0.6	2012/2/28	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
134	male	68	pre-treatment	2012/3/2	0.6	2012/3/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia	Opioid analgesics; α -glucosidase inhibitor
135	male	82	pre-treatment	2012/3/13	0.6	2012/3/13	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
136	male	80	post-treatment	2012/4/12	0.4	2012/4/13	negative	GERD; Coronary heart disease	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics
137	male	72	post-treatment	2012/4/12	0.8	2012/4/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
138	male	85	pre-treatment	2012/4/19	4.0	2012/4/20	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; COPD	
139	male	92	pre-treatment	2012/4/19	0.1	2012/4/13	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
140	male	81	pre-treatment	2012/4/26	0.8	2012/4/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
141	male	81	post-treatment	2012/5/25	0.4	2012/5/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
142	male	88	post-treatment	2012/5/25	0.60	2012/5/25	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
143	male	85	pre-treatment	2012/5/25	0.1	2012/5/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
144	male	69	pre-treatment	2012/6/5	0.3	2012/6/5	negative	Constipation; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
145	male	67	post-treatment	2012/6/5	1.4	2012/6/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
146	male	77	pre-treatment	2012/6/8	1.2	2012/6/1	negative	Gastric polyps	
147	male	87	pre-treatment	2012/6/13	45.4	2012/6/11	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Dementia; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
148	male	93	pre-treatment	2012/6/19	1.3	2012/6/15	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
149	male	86	pre-treatment	2012/7/6	46.2	2012/7/6	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps	
150	male	69	pre-treatment	2012/7/11	0.6	2012/7/13	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
151	male	86	post-treatment	2012/7/20	1.3	2012/7/20	negative	Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
152	male	68	pre-treatment	2012/7/24	0.6	2012/7/24	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
153	male	70	pre-treatment	2012/7/26	18.4	2012/7/20	positive	Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia	
154	male	89	post-treatment	2012/8/31	1.3	2012/8/28	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme
155	male	72	pre-treatment	2012/9/5	11.7	2012/9/11	positive	Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
156	male	81	pre-treatment	2012/9/11	1.4	2012/9/7	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; COPD; Dementia; Post-cerebral infarction	
157	male	83	pre-treatment	2012/9/28	0.4	2012/9/28	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
158	male	74	pre-treatment	2012/10/17	0.2	2012/10/16	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus	
159	male	83	pre-treatment	2012/10/29	18.4	2012/10/26	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
160	male	85	pre-treatment	2012/11/9	0.7	2012/11/3	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
161	male	71	pre-treatment	2012/11/13	5.3	2012/11/6	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
162	male	88	post-treatment	2012/11/22	4.6	2012/11/23	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents

163	male	90	pre-treatment	2012/11/22	4.9	2012/11/21	positive	Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
164	male	65	post-treatment	2012/11/22	0.1	2012/11/20	negative		
165	male	82	post-treatment	2012/11/29	0.6	2012/11/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents
166	male	86	pre-treatment	2012/12/8	0.70	2012/12/11	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
167	male	68	pre-treatment	2012/12/26	1.2	2012/12/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
168	male	65	pre-treatment	2013/1/14	0.1	2013/1/10	negative	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
169	male	69	post-treatment	2013/1/15	3.7	2013/1/11	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
170	male	70	post-treatment	2013/1/29	19.3	2013/1/23	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; History of intestinal surgery; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; COPD	Opioid analgesics
171	male	82	post-treatment	2013/3/26	0.3	2013/3/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Post-cerebral infarction	Opioid analgesics
172	male	66	pre-treatment	2013/3/29	0.2	2013/3/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
173	male	80	post-treatment	2013/4/19	1.30	2013/4/17	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Lipid-lowering agents
174	male	68	pre-treatment	2013/5/6	1.3	2013/5/10	negative	Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
175	male	74	pre-treatment	2013/5/8	0.7	2013/5/6	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus	
176	male	78	post-treatment	2013/5/14	0.5	2013/5/8	negative	Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
177	male	73	post-treatment	2013/6/7	0.3	2013/6/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
178	male	75	pre-treatment	2013/6/19	0.4	2013/6/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
179	male	75	pre-treatment	2013/6/19	0.4	2013/6/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
180	male	75	pre-treatment	2013/6/19	0.4	2013/6/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
181	male	81	post-treatment	2013/6/25	10.8	2013/6/24	positive	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
182	male	83	pre-treatment	2013/6/28	28.4	2013/6/27	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease	
183	male	89	pre-treatment	2013/7/2	46.5	2013/6/25	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; COPD	α -glucosidase inhibitor
184	male	89	pre-treatment	2013/7/2	46.5	2013/6/25	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; COPD	α -glucosidase inhibitor
185	male	86	post-treatment	2013/7/10	6.6	2013/7/3	positive	Atrophic gastritis; COPD	
186	male	86	post-treatment	2013/7/10	6.6	2013/7/3	positive	Atrophic gastritis; COPD	
187	male	83	pre-treatment	2013/7/18	0.8	2013/7/18	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
188	male	71	pre-treatment	2013/8/1	0.4	2013/7/27	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
189	male	71	pre-treatment	2013/8/1	0.4	2013/7/27	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
190	male	76	pre-treatment	2013/8/28	23.1	2013/8/26	positive	GERD	
191	male	89	post-treatment	2013/9/12	39.7	2013/9/10	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
192	male	89	post-treatment	2013/9/12	39.7	2013/9/10	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
193	male	66	post-treatment	2013/10/29	1.1	2013/10/23	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
194	male	66	post-treatment	2013/10/29	1.1	2013/10/23	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
195	male	72	pre-treatment	2013/11/7	0.8	2013/11/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
196	male	72	pre-treatment	2013/11/7	0.8	2013/11/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
197	male	88	post-treatment	2013/11/15	0.5	2013/11/15	negative	Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus	
198	male	88	post-treatment	2013/11/15	0.5	2013/11/15	negative	Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus	
199	male	85	pre-treatment	2013/11/29	0.5	2013/11/22	negative	GERD	
200	male	85	pre-treatment	2013/11/29	0.5	2013/11/22	negative	GERD	
201	male	69	pre-treatment	2013/12/6	0.90	2013/12/5	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps	
202	male	70	pre-treatment	2013/12/11	0.6	2013/12/9	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
203	male	70	pre-treatment	2013/12/11	0.6	2013/12/9	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents

204	male	70	post-treatment	2013/12/16	0.1	2013/12/18	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
205	male	70	post-treatment	2013/12/16	0.1	2013/12/18	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
206	male	81	post-treatment	2013/12/23	0.8	2013/12/24	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
207	male	76	pre-treatment	2014/1/8	1.2	2014/1/8	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
208	male	69	pre-treatment	2014/1/15	0.9	2014/1/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Opioid analgesics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
209	male	68	pre-treatment	2014/1/17	0.4	2014/1/16	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps	Opioid analgesics
210	male	80	pre-treatment	2014/2/11	1.7	2014/2/11	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
211	male	81	post-treatment	2014/2/13	20.0	2014/2/17	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
212	male	69	post-treatment	2014/2/13	0.4	2014/2/10	negative	History of intestinal surgery; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
213	male	69	post-treatment	2014/2/14	7.6	2014/2/14	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; COPD	
214	male	83	post-treatment	2014/2/20	1.0	2014/2/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
215	male	72	pre-treatment	2014/2/21	0.8	2014/2/25	negative	GERD; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Digestive enzyme; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
216	male	85	post-treatment	2014/2/21	0.6	2014/2/19	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Post-cerebral infarction	
217	male	82	post-treatment	2014/3/5	0.3	2014/2/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
218	male	67	pre-treatment	2014/3/10	3.4	2014/3/7	negative	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
219	male	71	pre-treatment	2014/3/12	3.2	2014/3/12	negative		
220	male	77	pre-treatment	2014/3/17	10.4	2014/3/19	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
221	male	87	pre-treatment	2014/3/18	0.2	2014/3/21	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
222	male	66	post-treatment	2014/3/19	20.4	2014/3/17	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum	
223	male	69	pre-treatment	2014/3/21	0.2	2014/3/24	negative	Gastric polyps	
224	male	87	pre-treatment	2014/3/27	0.1	2014/3/26	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
225	male	71	pre-treatment	2014/4/1	0.3	2014/4/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis	Prebiotics or probiotics; Lipid-lowering agents
226	male	74	pre-treatment	2014/4/1	1.1	2014/4/1	negative	GERD; Colon diverticulum; Hyperlipidemia	
227	male	74	post-treatment	2014/4/1	0.1	2014/3/29	negative	Atrophic gastritis	
228	male	74	post-treatment	2014/4/3	0.3	2014/4/1	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
229	male	78	pre-treatment	2014/4/11	0.1	2014/4/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
230	male	68	pre-treatment	2014/4/14	2.6	2014/4/12	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hypertension; COPD	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
231	male	84	pre-treatment	2014/4/17	4.6	2014/4/15	negative	GERD; Coronary heart disease	
232	male	81	pre-treatment	2014/5/22	0.2	2014/5/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
233	male	69	pre-treatment	2014/5/23	4.3	2014/5/23	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; COPD	Opioid analgesics; Prebiotics or probiotics
234	male	73	pre-treatment	2014/5/23	1.0	2014/5/22	negative	GERD; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
235	male	71	post-treatment	2014/5/23	1.0	2014/5/21	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Post-cerebral infarction	Opioid analgesics
236	male	83	pre-treatment	2014/5/26	1.5	2014/5/24	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease	
237	male	67	pre-treatment	2014/5/29	1.1	2014/5/29	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
238	male	65	pre-treatment	2014/5/29	0.1	2014/5/28	negative		
239	male	84	pre-treatment	2014/6/6	0.5	2014/6/5	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD	
240	male	71	pre-treatment	2014/6/11	1.2	2014/6/12	negative	Constipation	Opioid analgesics; Digestive enzyme
241	male	79	pre-treatment	2014/6/20	0.9	2014/6/19	negative	Gastric polyps	
242	male	85	pre-treatment	2014/6/30	0.6	2014/6/25	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
243	male	77	pre-treatment	2014/7/10	0.60	2014/7/10	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
244	male	91	pre-treatment	2014/7/11	2.1	2014/7/18	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Post-cerebral infarction	

245	male	90	post-treatment	2014/7/11	0.4	2014/7/11	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents
246	male	76	pre-treatment	2014/8/4	0.4	2014/7/31	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
247	male	68	pre-treatment	2014/8/7	1.2	2014/8/6	negative	Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
248	male	80	pre-treatment	2014/8/12	0.8	2014/8/12	negative	Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
249	male	95	post-treatment	2014/8/14	0.6	2014/8/11	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
250	male	79	pre-treatment	2014/8/28	0.4	2014/8/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
251	male	84	pre-treatment	2014/8/29	51.9	2014/8/28	positive	Diabetes mellitus	
252	male	68	post-treatment	2014/9/4	0.1	2014/9/3	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; COPD	
253	male	83	pre-treatment	2014/9/16	0.4	2014/9/12	negative	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
254	male	75	pre-treatment	2014/9/16	2.4	2014/9/11	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus	
255	male	75	pre-treatment	2014/9/16	2.4	2014/9/11	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus	
256	male	69	pre-treatment	2014/9/28	0.4	2014/10/1	negative	Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
257	male	87	pre-treatment	2014/11/17	2.0	2014/11/20	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
258	male	70	pre-treatment	2014/11/24	0.1	2014/11/24	negative	COPD	
259	male	72	post-treatment	2014/12/4	0.5	2014/12/1	negative	Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
260	male	80	pre-treatment	2014/12/11	0.8	2014/12/4	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Constipation; Gastric polyps; History of intestinal surgery; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
261	male	81	pre-treatment	2014/12/18	2.4	2014/12/17	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
262	male	67	pre-treatment	2014/12/30	0.90	2014/12/27	intermediate	Diabetes mellitus	
263	male	73	pre-treatment	2014/12/30	0.6	2014/12/26	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease	
264	male	85	pre-treatment	2015/1/15	0.8	2015/1/15	negative	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
265	male	85	pre-treatment	2015/1/15	0.8	2015/1/15	negative	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
266	male	67	post-treatment	2015/1/23	0.4	2015/1/21	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Constipation; History of intestinal surgery	Opioid analgesics
267	male	81	pre-treatment	2015/1/29	0.4	2015/1/28	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Gastric polyps; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
268	male	81	pre-treatment	2015/1/29	0.4	2015/1/28	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Gastric polyps; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
269	male	69	pre-treatment	2015/1/29	4.3	2015/1/26	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
270	male	89	post-treatment	2015/2/2	0.5	2015/1/30	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
271	male	89	pre-treatment	2015/3/2	4.3	2015/2/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease	Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
272	male	70	post-treatment	2015/3/2	0.5	2015/2/27	negative	History of intestinal surgery; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
273	male	68	pre-treatment	2015/3/5	0.5	2015/3/3	negative	GERD	Prokinetic agents; Prebiotics or probiotics
274	male	70	pre-treatment	2015/3/5	0.7	2015/2/28	negative	GERD; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
275	male	81	pre-treatment	2015/3/13	0.3	2015/3/10	negative	Constipation; Gastric polyps; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension; COPD	Prebiotics or probiotics; Digestive enzyme; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
276	male	67	post-treatment	2015/3/20	13.0	2015/3/16	positive	Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	Opioid analgesics
277	male	75	post-treatment	2015/3/24	0.1	2015/3/23	negative	Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
278	male	75	post-treatment	2015/3/24	0.1	2015/3/23	negative	Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
279	male	88	post-treatment	2015/4/14	9.6	2015/4/14	positive	Atrophic gastritis; COPD	
280	male	80	pre-treatment	2015/4/15	1.0	2015/4/14	negative	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
281	male	76	pre-treatment	2015/4/16	0.6	2015/4/13	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus	
282	male	76	pre-treatment	2015/5/7	1.6	2015/5/6	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
283	male	88	pre-treatment	2015/6/11	1.0	2015/6/12	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents
284	male	88	pre-treatment	2015/6/11	1.0	2015/6/12	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antihypertensive agents
285	male	75	post-treatment	2015/6/12	0.6	2015/6/12	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents

286	male	75	post-treatment	2015/6/12	0.6	2015/6/12	negative	Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
287	male	82	post-treatment	2015/6/19	0.2	2015/6/18	negative	Colon diverticulum; Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
288	male	67	pre-treatment	2015/6/19	0.2	2015/6/16	positive	Constipation	Antiplatelet agents; Lipid-lowering agents
289	male	67	post-treatment	2015/6/30	0.1	2015/6/26	negative	Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
290	male	79	pre-treatment	2015/7/16	3.50	2015/7/17	intermediate	Coronary heart disease	Antiplatelet agents
291	male	69	post-treatment	2015/9/22	39.4	2015/9/22	positive	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
292	male	87	post-treatment	2015/9/25	1.4	2015/9/23	negative	Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; COPD	
293	male	84	post-treatment	2015/9/29	0.8	2015/9/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
294	male	82	pre-treatment	2015/10/12	0.9	2015/10/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
295	male	69	pre-treatment	2015/10/12	26.20	2015/10/9	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents; α -glucosidase inhibitor
296	male	70	pre-treatment	2015/10/30	3.2	2015/10/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps	
297	male	84	pre-treatment	2015/11/2	1.1	2015/10/31	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
298	male	84	pre-treatment	2015/11/2	1.1	2015/10/31	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
299	male	85	pre-treatment	2015/11/26	0.2	2015/11/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease	
300	male	85	pre-treatment	2015/11/26	0.2	2015/11/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease	
301	male	73	post-treatment	2016/2/2	0.1	2016/1/28	negative	Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
302	male	67	pre-treatment	2016/3/18	0.6	2016/3/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
303	male	79	pre-treatment	2016/3/18	0.1	2016/3/16	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Coronary heart disease	Antiplatelet agents
304	male	73	pre-treatment	2016/5/19	0.9	2016/5/20	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
305	male	88	post-treatment	2016/6/8	0.9	2016/6/6	negative	Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
306	male	76	post-treatment	2016/7/11	0.5	2016/7/6	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps	
307	male	67	post-treatment	2016/8/9	1.80	2016/8/8	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
308	male	66	pre-treatment	2016/10/18	0.6	2016/10/14	negative	Colorectal polyps; History of intestinal surgery; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
309	male	85	post-treatment	2017/2/8	0.9	2017/2/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Constipation; Colon diverticulum; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
310	male	68	pre-treatment	2017/2/23	0.1	2017/2/27	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
311	male	86	post-treatment	2017/2/27	0.3	2017/2/24	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
312	male	88	pre-treatment	2017/3/3	0.2	2017/3/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps	Opioid analgesics
313	male	88	pre-treatment	2017/3/3	0.2	2017/3/2	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; Colorectal polyps	Opioid analgesics
314	male	69	post-treatment	2017/3/15	0.9	2017/3/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Constipation; Colorectal polyps; History of intestinal surgery	Opioid analgesics
315	male	86	post-treatment	2017/4/17	0.9	2017/4/14	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
316	male	79	pre-treatment	2017/4/19	1.8	2017/4/19	negative	GERD; Colorectal polyps	
317	male	95	post-treatment	2017/4/27	2.3	2017/4/22	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
318	male	90	post-treatment	2017/5/25	0.6	2017/5/24	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Constipation; COPD	
319	male	94	pre-treatment	2017/6/2	1.2	2017/6/2	negative	Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Post-cerebral infarction	Prebiotics or probiotics; Antiplatelet agents
320	male	95	post-treatment	2017/6/7	10.9	2017/6/13	positive	Atrophic gastritis; Diabetes mellitus; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
321	male	68	pre-treatment	2017/9/18	1.60	2017/9/18	intermediate	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antiplatelet agents; Antihypertensive agents
322	male	94	post-treatment	2018/3/14	1.6	2018/3/10	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
323	male	74	pre-treatment	2018/4/2	1.6	2018/3/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents; Lipid-lowering agents
324	male	73	post-treatment	2018/5/16	0.7	2018/5/16	positive	Hyperlipidemia; Post-cerebral infarction	
325	male	88	pre-treatment	2018/5/28	1.4	2018/5/25	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colorectal polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
326	male	89	post-treatment	2018/5/31	0.4	2018/5/31	negative	Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Antihypertensive agents

327	male	74	pre-treatment	2018/7/23	1.2	2018/7/24	positive	Constipation; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; Post-cerebral infarction	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
328	male	76	post-treatment	2018/8/16	0.7	2018/8/16	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
329	male	77	pre-treatment	2018/9/19	0.3	2018/9/17	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hypertension	Opioid analgesics; Antihypertensive agents
330	male	82	post-treatment	2018/10/18	0.4	2018/10/18	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Colon diverticulum; Gastric polyps; Diabetes mellitus; Coronary heart disease	
331	male	65	post-treatment	2018/10/30	0.7	2018/10/26	negative	GERD; Diabetes mellitus; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension	Antihypertensive agents
332	male	82	post-treatment	2018/11/7	0.3	2018/11/6	negative	Colorectal polyps; Coronary heart disease; Hypertension; COPD	Antihypertensive agents
333	male	90	pre-treatment	2018/11/23	0.8	2018/11/20	negative	Atrophic gastritis; GERD; Constipation	
334	male	87	pre-treatment	2018/11/29	0.2	2018/11/30	negative	Atrophic gastritis; Hyperlipidemia; Coronary heart disease	
